

ABCSalt

Advanced Biomass
Catalytic Conversion

COMSYN

**NEXT GENERATION
BIO-FUEL TECHNOLOGY**

SPRING SCHOOL 2nd GENERATION BIOFUELS

*How to Maximize the Output
of Your Research Project?*

17 – 18 MARCH 2021

Online Event

DLR

SPRING SCHOOL 2nd GENERATION BIOFUELS

by ABC-SALT & COMSYN

Who can participate?

- PhD students
- Young researchers from all disciplines, from social to natural sciences and engineering

You will benefit from:

- Lectures on 2nd generation biofuels and project development
- Meeting with renowned international researchers and experts involved in European funded projects
- Creativity sessions on developing soft skills, with specific attention to maximize impact of your own research
- Interactive workshop on addressing interdisciplinary aspects in the project proposal preparation

Highlights:

- Best presentation award
- Best project award
- No participation fees!
- Up to 50 participants
- Registration mandatory: "First come, first served"

APPLY NOW

More information and registration at: <https://dlr.expert/spring-school-biofuels/>
For any enquiries, please contact: spring-school-biofuels@dlr.de

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